

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Testing Ice with Flex TPS

The following Application Highlight addresses testing of samples in subambient conditions using the Flex TPS module with C-Therm's Trident.

Many groups want to test their materials at subambient conditions to get a better idea of the thermal behavior of the material under the conditions of application – for example, material for an Arctic installation might be tested at -30°C to ensure it will withstand the harsh conditions without losing thermal performance. C-Therm's Trident TPS module can be used to test materials in subambient conditions, using an optional thermal chamber and test clamp assembly.

Figure 1. Ice has a thermal conductivity over 3X higher than water.

Sample preparation was straightforward for the testing of ice: The sensor was submerged in degassed deionized water in a paper cup and then frozen overnight. As the ice cracked on freezing, cracks were filled with more deionized water and then the sample was refrozen to ensure good thermal contact. The wooden sticks were used as a placement aid to ensure the sensor alignment remained good during sample preparation and testing. Following crack-filling and re-freezing in a thermal chamber, the paper cup used to prepare the sample was removed, yielding the sensor embedded in a block of ice as shown below.

Figure 2. C-Therm Flex TPS Thermal Conductivity Sensor Embedded in Ice.

Thermal conductivity test data generated with the C-Therm TCkit is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Thermal Conductivity of Ice.

In this case, the reference data set is an aggregate of 4 literature data sets on the thermal conductivity of ice.¹ The average of the four is reported here. Error bars represent the relative standard deviation of the experimental and reference data set. At all four temperature points the agreement between experimental and literature data is better than the aggregate precision of the data sets, indicating very good agreement between the experimental data and the test data.

This application highlight demonstrates the effectiveness of applying Trident TPS in characterizing the thermal conductivity of samples at subambient temperature conditions.

To learn more about C-Therm's Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit www.TridentThermalConductivity.com

¹ Ratcliffe, E.H. The Thermal Conductivity of Ice New Data on the Temperature Coefficient. *Philosophical Magazine* 1962, 7, 1197–1203.;
Alexiades, V.; Solomon, A.D. *Mathematical Modeling of Melting and Freezing Processes*; Hemisphere Publishing: Washington, 1993.;
Lunardini, V.J. *Heat Transfer in Cold Climates*; Van Nostrand Reinhold: New York, 1981.;
Waite, W.F.; Gilbert, L.Y.; Winters, W.J.; Mason, D.H. Estimating Thermal Diffusivity and Specific Heat from Needle Probe Thermal Conductivity Data. *Review of Scientific Instruments* 2006, 77, 044904.